

One Dimensional Reflection/Refraction, Spatial Invariance and the Emergence of $\exp(ipx)$

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A one dimensional reflection/refraction problem is by nature probabilistic because an incident photon either reflects or refracts with certain unknown probabilities. The problem is traditionally solved by matching the electric field and its derivative with respect to x at $x=0$, $t=0$ where the electric field for a photon follows from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations and is given by $E_0 \cos(-\omega t + kx)$ where $p = \hbar k$. As such, this problem is treated "classically" We argue, however, that this is a quantum mechanical problem (the photon being a quantum particle). Furthermore, no information is needed about the form of the electric field.

Reflection/refraction conserves energy. It also occurs at some x point which may be varied i.e. there is translational invariance. A conservation of energy equation may be immediately written. The first medium has an index of refraction $n_1=1$ and the second $n_2 < n_1$. The conservation of energy equation is: $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ where AA , BB and CC are the incident, reflected and refracted intensities = energy per photon * speed * number of photons. AA etc. is written to show that the intensity is explicitly positive. If one considers A known, then B and C are two unknowns, but there is only one equation. Thus energy conservation is not the full reality or information of the problem.

This problem may be mathematically solved by using a difference of squares which leads to two equations: $(A+B) = C$ and $p_1(A-B) = p_2 C$. These may be solved for B, C in terms of A . This, however, is not the most general solution in that it does not show invariance of x i.e. the point at which the index of refraction changes. In this note we investigate the consequences of including x in the solution and argue this leads to a kind of square-root probability function which together with its first derivative should be continuous at any x chosen to be the interface of the media. This leads to a solution of $A \exp(ipx)$, instead of A (etc), which is the free particle wavefunction. Thus this wavefunction (or unusual probability) is a direct consequence of the spatial invariance in the problem, but ensures that no x dependence appears if one combines the two square-root probability equations to create an energy conservation equation which has nothing to do with x .

Traditional One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

Consider a photon moving along the positive x axis which strikes a medium interface $n_1=1$ and $n_2 > n_1$ at some x_0 . There is x invariance and this is information which really should be included in any full solution. If one wishes, however, to only know the probability to reflect and refract, then x_0 is irrelevant in the sense that it does not appear in the solution. Nevertheless, we argue it is relevant information to the problem overall and should not disappear. Including it yields important consequences, namely the free particle wavefunction, which ultimately leads to interference/diffraction patterns.

A photon is described by $E=pc$ where E is energy, p momentum and c speed. The incident, reflected and refracted photons all have the same energy E . Traditionally the reflection/refraction problem is solved "classically" using Maxwell's solution for the electric field of a photon from his electromagnetic equations. This is given by $E_0 \cos(-\omega t + kx)$ where $p = \hbar k$

k. One writes two equations, namely a continuity of the electric field and its first derivative with respect to x at the arbitrarily chosen $x=0$, $t=0$ to make the problem simple. One then solves for amplitudes of the reflected and refracted beams in terms of the incident. The energy density of a photon in electromagnetism is proportional to Electric field * Electric field so one may obtain an energy conservation equation by squaring the amplitudes.

Energy Conservation A Priori

For the case of a photon reflecting/refracting with the energy constant, one may consider an energy flux or intensity of: $E \cdot \text{speed} \cdot \text{number of photons}$ and write an energy conservation equation a priori without knowing anything about the electric field for a photon.

In particular:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((1)) \quad \text{Here } c_1=c \text{ because } n_1=1 \text{ and } c_2=c/n.$$

A represents the incident beam, B the reflected and C the refracted. AA etc is written to show that intensity is strictly positive.

((1)) is one equation in two unknowns, assuming A is known. The problem may, however, be solved by writing: $AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/c_2$ and using $E = p_1 c_1 = p_2 c_2$. A difference of squares may be written as two equations which may be solved for B and C in terms of A i.e.

$$A+B = C \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p_1 A - p_1 B = p_2 C \quad ((2b)) \quad (\text{Note: } E=pc)$$

For $n_2 > n_1$, B is negative. Once B and C are known in terms of A one may return to the energy conservation equation ((1))

Thus the notion of x_0 , the interface x point, and its invariance do not appear at all when simply trying to find B and C in terms of A. We argue, however, that x invariance is information which should ultimately appear in the solution, at least at the square root probability level i.e the A but not AA level.

The Idea of X Invariance

For reflection/refraction at x_0 there is spatial invariance. This does not affect the probability to reflect/refract BB,CC in terms of AA, but it is physical information which should not simply disappear, we argue. How does one then incorporate it into the solution of the problem which relies on writing a difference of squares in terms of two equations?

We argue that x should be introduced via a function $F(x, \pi)$ as these are the two relevant pieces of information. As a result, $F(x, \pi)$ takes on the form of a kind of probability. It seems this is the interpretation of $F(x, \pi)$. As a result, one may insist on the continuity of x probability (with time removed as in a steady flow picture) at an arbitrary x_0 and also on the continuity of its derivative d/dx , the generator of translations, in this translationally invariant problem. Then, arranging the equations spatially:

$$AF(x_0, p_1) + BF(x_0, -p_1) = C F(x_0, p_2) \quad ((3a))$$

$$\text{And } A \frac{dF(p_1)}{dx} (\text{at } x_0) + B \frac{dF(-p_1)}{dx} (\text{at } x_0) = C \frac{dF(p_2)}{dx} \quad ((3b))$$

Comparing ((3b)) with ((2b)) suggests: $\frac{dF(p_i)}{dx} = \text{constant } p_i F(p_i, x)$. Thus F is an eigenfunction of d/dx with eigenvalue constant p_i . The next requirement is that the energy conservation equation should remain unchanged. Thus BB and CC as well as AA should show no x dependence. This seems to imply the presence of complex numbers such that AA really means A^*A . A solution to this problem is:

$$F(x, p) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ is a two dimensional periodic probability as well as being an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$ which is $-i$ times the translation generator. $F(x, p)$ is introduced in the first place in order to take account of the translational invariance information in the problem. Given that one matches square root probabilities at x_0 (which already indicates x invariance), the translational generator appears when one matches first derivatives.

((4)) has major implications. Although its modulus is 1 and so it does not affect energy conservation, it suggests a two dimensional periodic behaviour in x in order to maintain or physically create the sense of spatial invariance. Furthermore if one had a photon trapped in a box without considering time and one treats $\exp(ipx)$ as a kind of probability then:

$$\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) = 2 \cos(px) \quad ((5))$$

The $\cos(px)$ pattern is real and its modulus is $\cos(px) \cos(px)$ which leads to a spatially visible result. Furthermore, interference and diffraction patterns associated with $\exp(ipx)$ also lead to visible results.

Thus insisting that a particular piece of information, namely spatial invariance, appear in a solution of square root probabilities, even though it is not needed for the energy conservation equation leads to $\exp(ipx)$. It may be noted that the conservation of energy equation does not have enough information to solve for the probabilities of reflection and refraction in terms of the incident intensity. Thus, even though it may at first appear to capture the information of the problem i.e. the reality of the problem, it does not. The reality lies at the square root probability level and includes the notion of spatial invariance.

One might even suggest that the absence of x in the conservation of energy, even though the interface is at x_0 , implies that the full information of the problem is missing.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that even though the problem of one dimensional reflection/refraction may be solved traditionally by matching Maxwell's photonic electric field and its derivative d/dx at the arbitrary point $x=0, t=0$, one does not need the electric field to solve the problem. One may

simply write the conservation of energy equation in terms of fluxes: $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ where A,B,C represent the incident, reflected and refracted beams and AA etc indicates that intensity is strictly positive. This equation then may be rearranged as a difference of squares and written as two equations. With two equations, the two unknowns B,C may be solved for in terms of A. Thus, reality or complete information is not present in the single energy conservation equation, even though one might consider it to be.

We suggest that a further piece of information is missing from this approach, namely that of x invariance. The interface of media may be placed at any x_0 point and the probabilities BB and CC do not change. It would be good for this invariance to appear explicitly in the problem. In such a case, we write $1/c$ as $E/c = p$ because E is constant. P represents impulse and we choose this value over c. Next, we introduce a function $F(p,x)$ as a kind of probability. If the function and its first derivative d/dx are continuous at any x, then one has two equations. In order to match the two difference of squares equations, we require that $d/dx F(p,x) = \text{constant } p F(p,x)$. The overall result, however, must yield the conservation of energy equation with no x present. This suggests: $F(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$ or the wavefunction of a photon which has implications such as two slit diffraction patterns etc.